

PRINCIPALS' ADMINISTRATIVE BEHAVIOUR AND TEACHERS' JOB EFFECTIVENESS IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study investigated the extent to which principals' administrative behaviour predicts teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. The principals' administrative behaviour variable was, instructional supervision. A research question and null hypothesis guided the study. Correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 762 principals (254 principals and 508 vice principals) and 7,388 teachers in the 254 public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. One thousand, one hundred and eighty-four respondents were selected as sample for the study, which consist of 399 principals and 785 teachers randomly selected from the 254 public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. Multi-stage sampling approach was used for the study. Data collection was carried out with the use of two research instruments titled 'Principals' Administrative Behaviour Questionnaire (PABQ) and Teachers' Job Effectiveness Questionnaire (TJEQ). The instruments were subjected to face validity by two research experts. The reliability of the instruments was established using Cronbach Alpha reliability statistic. The reliability indices for both instruments were .968 and .830 respectively. These figures confirmed that the instruments were reliable in achieving the objective of the study. Simple linear regression statistics was used to test the null hypothesis at .05 level of significance. Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that principals' administrative behaviour significantly predicts teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. It is therefore recommended among others, that Professional development of principals aimed at supporting teachers' job effectiveness should be given adequate attention by the government.

Keywords:

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background Issues

Teachers' job effectiveness goes beyond just imparting knowledge but it is a purposeful activity carried out by someone with specialized knowledge in a skillful way to enhance the cognitive, affective and psychomotor development of a person or group of persons. Sullivan (2001) posited that teachers' job effectiveness means to

demonstrate knowledge of the curriculum, provide instruction in a variety of approaches to varied students and measurably increases students' achievements. Uchefuna, (2001) asserted that teacher effectiveness has been conceptualized as producing desired results in the course of discharging duty as a teacher. Teachers' effectiveness can be determined in relation to the achievement of set goals.

Consequently, an effective teacher is one who helps students in the attainment of educational goals. Teachers' job effectiveness therefore can be assessed by students' performance. If students show signs of having learnt meaningfully, then the teacher can be said to be effective. According to Bongotons (2009), an effective teacher is one who keeps herself abreast in her field and is able to communicate her subject matter. An effective teacher should know when to teach, what to teach, how to teach and assess students level of understanding and if necessary re-teach. This is to make sure that more than three quarters of the students understood the subject matter and are capable of passing any examination on it.

An effective teacher is seen here as one who attains these objectives. Therefore, these definitions imply that teachers' job effectiveness is often associated with the degree to which a teacher uses desirable skills in task performance and the level of students' achievements in examinations. The personality traits that make a teacher effective are largely inborn. A few may be acquired through training, but a person who is born to be interested in working with people and who has personal characteristic such as patience, love for children, interest in helping others, a sense of humor; a pleasant personality, smartness, sympathy, alertness, good human relations, emotional stability among others, will certainly be more effective as a teacher. Such attributes as skills in imparting knowledge, scholarliness, good judgment and professional ethics can be acquired through training. An effective teacher is thus born and made (Denga 2002).

However, with the researcher's visit to some public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, it was observed that there are problems that constitute ineffectiveness as related to the teachers. Some teachers hardly make out time to relate with their students, take their lessons accordingly or even listen to their problems. Some students are preferred to others for trivial reasons, ranging from, students' tribe, relationship with parents and others. It was observed that some teachers decide whether to work with the principal or not, without minding the effects it will have on the students. In some instances, a level 15 teacher is relegated to the background while a level 12 teacher is involved in taking major decisions in the school. This could make a teacher to put up a laissez-faire attitude which may result to ineffectiveness. Some teachers do not have respect for their principals claiming that they strip them of every authority with the slogan "wait for your time". Some teachers are disorganized that they do not have the scheme of work to prepare their lessons before going to the class. They rather yell at

students, fail to give prompt feedback and discourage students from asking questions in the class. It was observed that this show of teachers' ineffectiveness could be as a result of some principals' administrative behaviour that they found demeaning. Thus the principal needs to acquire and exhibit positive administrative behaviour, like instructional supervision to function effectively as a school administrator. It is right to say that teachers' job effectiveness could directly or indirectly depend on the principals' administrative behaviour. This is because this principal's administrative behaviour highlighted could enhance teachers' job effectiveness if adequately used by the principal.

The principal holds a key position in the administration of secondary schools. He gives necessary advice and guidance to teachers, students and other members of the school. As an important component of the school administration the principal has important roles and responsibilities to play. Everything in the school, the plant, the staff, the curriculum, methods and techniques of teaching, co- curricular activities, are organized by him. The internal efficiency of the school which includes judicious use of all resources to attain education and school set goals depend on the ability, skill, personality and professional competence of the principal. He or she to a large extent may be described as the pillar that holds secondary education system. The principal is responsible for the smooth running of the school. The progress, development and health of the institution depend on the administrative behaviour of the principal.

Swargiary (2017) defined administrative behaviour as the process affecting the interpretation of events for the organisation to motivate its members to achieve the objectives and the maintenance of cooperative relationships and team work. It is the commitment of the decision makers to act, thereby committing the personnel, material and financial resources of the organisation. The principal plays a dominant role in the school and all the activities taking place in the institution revolves round him.

The administrative behaviour of principals is necessary in realizing schools' goals and objectives. What the principal say, do, or think, may have direct or indirect effect on teachers' job effectiveness. This is because their behaviours and abilities are central to the task of building schools that could promote effective teaching and learning for all students. Therefore, principals are in the position to influence the teachers, instruction delivery, students' performance, and the efficiency in the functioning of school. The hallmark of achieving teachers' job effectiveness begins with creating conducive school environment for all. Oyedeji & Fasasi (2006) regarded a school principal as the chief executive of the school, who is responsible for all that, happens in the school. The position the principal occupies places him in a great position to coordinate the entire school and move it forward. According to Ross and Gray (2006), when leadership in an organization is effective, there is progress but

when the leadership is defective, the organization declines and decays. The school needs leadership with proven administrative behaviour to strive for excellence. The responsibility of motivating the staff and improving the academic performance and general standards within the school lies solely on the principal. When they perform their duties well, the academic performance is likely to improve, (Muyiera, 2002). The Principal can play his role effectively in achieving the objectives of education policy only when he has the requisite behaviour which can help to encourage teachers' job effectiveness, hence the achievement of educational goals.

The concern of the principal of secondary school is to direct the activities of teachers in the school towards the attainment of teachers' job effectiveness. The principal is entrusted with the responsibility of supervising teachers generally to improve their instructional effectiveness. Meanwhile, it takes confidence to become a successful supervisor. A supervisor's job is to establish goals and lead a team of people to achieve them. The super-ordinate steps out with new creative ideas that save money, increase productivity and establish credibility and respect from subordinates. Supervision has the capacity of impacting much on the effectiveness of the teacher's job. For instance, it has been observed that some principals do not set up their strategy to either supervise teachers' use of time, check how materials and supplies are utilized, coordinate student bodies to assist the teacher nor make sure that teachers' notes of lessons are up-to-date; thus this could be the reason why allegation of ineffectiveness of teaches now take a front burner in most forum of education stakeholders.

According to Tesfaw & Hofman (2014), instructional supervision is the supervision carried out by the head teacher, subject heads, and other assigned supervisors in a school with the aim of providing guidance and support to teachers. Zepeda (2010) on the other hand looks at instructional supervision as the continuous monitoring of classroom teaching with the aim of not only promoting professional practices, but also to enhance professional development in a collegial and collaborative style. In fact, Zepeda (2010) expresses that instructional supervision occurs in two main ways, namely: classroom observations (formal and informal) and portfolio supervision. Therefore, it has been identified that the primary purpose of instructional supervision process is to support and sustain all teachers in their goal of professional development, which ultimately results in quality instruction. Such growth and development rely on a system that is built on trust and is supportive of teachers' efforts to be more effective in their classrooms (Beach & Reinhartz, 2000).

Consequently, several studies related to principals' administrative behaviour such as instructional supervision have been conducted. Egbe (2010) researched on principals' instructional supervision and secondary school teachers' effectiveness in Calabar municipal council of Cross River State. The findings revealed that there was

a significant relationship between principals' instructional supervision and teachers' effectiveness in lesson presentation. This study was aimed at investigating the influence of principals' instructional supervision on teachers' teaching effectiveness in Akwa Ibom State secondary schools. To achieve this aim,

One hypothesis was formulated to guide the study and tested with analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Fishers (LSD) multiple comparison analysis at .05 level of significance. The population consisted of all the principals and teachers in the area, and stratified random sampling method was respectively used to draw out the sample size of 50 principals and 400 teachers. Data for the study were obtained through the aid of modified six point Likert scale researchers-constructed instruments called Principals' Instructional Supervision Questionnaire (PISQ) and Teachers' Teaching Effectiveness Questionnaire (TTEQ). The data analyzed revealed a significant influence of principals' instructional supervision on teachers' teaching effectiveness in Akwa Ibom State secondary schools. This was followed by some recommendations

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1.2 Statement of the Problem

The issue of teachers' job effectiveness in Akwa Ibom State Secondary Schools has generated concerns from the public. This is because it is alleged that because teachers do not put in their best at work, they are unable to produce students who will fit into the society and be useful to themselves and the society. Visits to some public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State revealed that most of the schools are operating under lack of cooperation, collaboration, less involvement and participation as well as poor mutual relationship between principals and teachers. The quality of secondary school teachers in recent times has been of great concern despite the notable efforts by the principals to ensure the right type of education for secondary school students. The problem of students' poor performance in school can be largely

traced to teachers' job ineffectiveness. This is so because, it is the teacher on whose shoulder lay the actual work of teaching.

It has been observed that there is laxity in the way teachers perform their roles. Teachers sometimes take advantage of principals' administrative behaviour which could make or mar teachers' job effectiveness in order to achieve their selfish ambitions. Some teachers do not write their lesson notes nor make proper use of diaries, schemes of work, and continuous assessment records. Teachers are frequently late to school and even stay away from school without good reasons. It is observed that some teachers fail to maintain discipline in the classroom, exhibiting inappropriate behavior towards the students. Teachers sometimes unfairly prefer some students to others, thereby decreasing students desire to learn. In some cases, teachers take up second occupation like trading. They sell their wares in the school and worst of all in the classroom. Some teachers demand for money from the principal to support his administration. This behavior to some extent could rob teachers of integrity and effectiveness in their profession.

This may be right but there are several factors that could be responsible for this unfortunate situation. This kindled the interest of the researcher which lies on the fact that the quality of education received by secondary school students in Akwa Ibom State continued to dwindle irrespective of the efforts principals claim to have made to enhance teachers' job effectiveness. One of the principals' administrative behaviour variable which seem to affect teachers' job effectiveness of public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State is principals' instructional supervision. A school principal who is not properly equipped with this fundamental behaviour used in improving teachers' job effectiveness may find it challenging in providing direction that would stimulate better teachers' effectiveness. Consequently, the study seeks to ascertain the extent to which principals' Administrative behaviour predicts teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. The problem of this study therefore is; to what extent does principals' administrative behaviour predict teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools?

1.3 Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to determine the extent to which principals' administrative behaviour predicts teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study is to determine the extent which: principals' instructional supervision predicts teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools.

1.4 Research Question

To what extent does principals' instructional supervision predict teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools?

1.5 Research Hypothesis

Principals' instructional supervision does not significantly predict teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Also, Etudor-Eyo, Etor, Akuegwu & Etokebe (2006) investigated the influence of principals' instructional supervision on teachers' teaching effectiveness in Akwa Ibom State secondary schools. The data analyzed revealed a significant influence of principals' instructional supervision on teachers' teaching effectiveness in Akwa Ibom State secondary schools. This implies that proper instructional supervision can improve teachers' productivity. Sule, Arop and Alade (2012) researched on principals' classroom visitation and inspection, and Teachers' Job Performance in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The result of the analysis shows that the F-ratio for one-way ANOVA of Principals' classroom visitation/observation and teachers Job Performance is 134.465, which is greater than the critical F (3.04) at $\alpha = 0.05$. This means that there is a significant influence of principals' classroom visitation and inspection on teachers' classroom management, instructional ability and student evaluation. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected since there is significance in terms of total job performance. Therefore, when the process of delivering the educational service is monitored, checked, encouraged and improved for efficiency and effectiveness, the end product would be of high quality.

Empirically, Nzabonimpa (2011) examined the influence of secondary school head teachers' general and instructional supervisory practices on teachers' work performance. The study findings revealed that to some teacher participants, supervision is non-existent in secondary schools due the fact that some of them have been teaching for more than a decade, but they have never been supervised by the head teacher in the classroom. The research findings likewise indicate a moderate correlation between secondary school head teacher's supervisory practices and teacher's work performance. The empirical study reviewed is relevant to this study due to its enlightenment on the importance of the principals' instructional supervision to teachers' job performances

[Sule, Ameh, Mercy & Egbai](#) (2015), in their study investigated the relationship between instructional supervisory practices and teachers' role effectiveness in public secondary schools in Calabar South Local Government Area of Cross River State. The result of the analysis revealed that there was a significant positive relationship between instructional supervisory practice of classroom observation and teachers' role effectiveness. The result also revealed that, there was a significant positive relationship between instructional supervisory practice of checking of teachers' lesson notes and teachers' role effectiveness. It was concluded that a closer, regular and continuous instructional supervisory practice rather than snappy, unscheduled

and partial supervision is what is urgently needed especially now that a lot of changes have been introduced into the school curriculum.

Iroegbu & Etudor-Eyo (2016) conducted a study on the topic, Principals' Instructional Supervision and Teachers' Effectiveness in Public Secondary Schools in Uyo Education Committee of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The study examined differences in teachers' effectiveness based on principals' instructional supervision in public secondary schools in Uyo Local Education Committee in Akwa Ibom State. The findings were that there is a significant difference in teachers' effectiveness based on classroom observation, analysis/strategy, post-conference analysis and post-analysis conference.

Umaru (2018) conducted a study titled "principals' instructional supervision and teachers performance in secondary schools in Danko Wasagu local area of Kebbi state Nigeria. The objective of the study was to determine the relationship between principals' instructional supervision and teachers' performance. Findings revealed that there was a significant relationship between principals' instructional supervision and teachers' job effectiveness. It is upon this background that this study on principals' administrative behaviour and teachers' job effectiveness was conducted.

3 RESEARCH METHOD

3.1 Study Design

The study adopted the correlational research design. correlational research design was deemed appropriate for this study because it investigated the extent which independent variable (instructional supervision) predicts the dependent variable (teachers' job effectiveness). The area for this study was Akwa Ibom State of Nigeria with focus on the public secondary schools in the State. The population of the study consists of all the principals, vice principals and teachers in the 254 public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. The population is therefore made up of 762 principals, (254 principals and 508 Vice Principals) including 7,388 teachers. These make for a total study population of 8,150 in the 254 public secondary schools in the 31 Local Government Areas of Akwa Ibom State as at 2020/2021 academic year (Akwa Ibom State Statistic Division of the State Secondary Education Board, Uyo, 2020).

The sample size for the study comprised 399 principals (133 principals and 266 vice principals) and 785 teachers representing 52% and 20% of the population of principals and teachers respectively in the sampled schools. The study adopted Multi-stage sampling technique. First stage, cluster sampling technique was used to group the State into three clusters representing the three Senatorial Districts of Akwa Ibom State. Proportionate sampling approach was used to select 40% from the public secondary schools in each of the sampled Local Government Areas in each of the three senatorial districts in Akwa Ibom State to give 133 schools. Simple random

sampling technique was used to select 20% of teachers, in each sampled school. In the next stage, purposive sampling technique was used to include the principals and vice principal's administration and academics in the selected public secondary schools. This gave a total number of 399 principals. To sample the teachers, 20% was selected from the sampled schools using proportionate sampling approach, and this gave 785 teachers. In each of the sampled schools, simple random sampling of hat and draw method was used to select 20% of teachers. The teachers selected responded to the Principals' Administrative Behaviour Questionnaire (PABQ) while principals responded to Teachers' job Effectiveness Questionnaire (TJEQ). The mean score of the ratings of the teachers was the score for one principal. Teachers formed the unit of analysis because the problem of this study is focused on the teachers.

Two instruments tagged "Principals' Administrative Behaviour Questionnaire" (PABQ) and "Teachers Job Effectiveness Questionnaire" (TJEQ) were used to collect data for the study. Teachers are to respond to the Principals' Administrative Behaviour Questionnaire (PABQ) while principals responded to "Teachers' Job Effectiveness Questionnaire. The instruments were scored using a four- point rating scale for positively worded items, while the score for negatively worded items was reversed. Principals' Administrative Behaviour Questionnaire (PABQ) was scored using: VHE = Very Highly Effective (5 points). HE = Highly Effective (4 points). ME = Moderately Effective (3 points). LE = Low Effectiveness (2 points). VLE = Very low Effectiveness (1 point) while "Teachers' Job Effectiveness Questionnaire" (TJEQ) was scored using: VHE = Very High Extent (5 points). HE = High Extent (4 points). ME = Moderate Extent (3 points). LE = Low Extent (2 points). VLE = Very Low Extent (1 point). To determine the teachers' job effectiveness, the theoretical mean response of 2.5 is used. When the mean score falls below 2.5, it is classified ineffective while 2.5 and above are classified effective.

The questionnaires were validated by three research experts. The reliability of the instrument was determined using internal consistency method, while the reliability indices for the instruments were calculated using Cronbach Alpha statistic. Decision was based on the reliability coefficients obtained for the two instruments. The reliability indices for both instruments were .968 for PABQ and .830 for TEQ respectively, confirming that the instruments were reliable in achieving the objectives of the study.

3.2 Method of Data Analysis

Data collected was analyzed using Simple Linear Regression Statistic. This method of data analysis is considered appropriate since it was used to investigate the extent to which Principals' Administrative Behaviour predicts Teachers' Job Effectiveness. The research question was answered using the R- value of the simple linear regression. This was used to determine the strength of extent of relationship between

the dependent and independent variables, while the null hypothesis was tested using F-ratio at 0.05 level of significance.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Research Question

To what extent does principals' Instructional Supervision predicts teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State?

Table 1: Result of Simple Linear Regression of extent to which principals' Instructional Supervision predicts teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State (n=778)

Variables	R	R ²	Extent of R ²	Adjusted	Remark
Principals' Instructional Supervision					Very High
Teachers' Job Effectiveness	0.910	0.828	82.8%	0.828	Prediction

Table 1 reveals that the calculated R value is 0.910 and R² value of 0.828 which represent strength of prediction and coefficient of determination of the extent of prediction respectively. The R value indicates that there is high prediction between principals' instructional supervision and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, while R² indicates that 82.8 % of variation in teachers' job effectiveness is accounted for by principals' instructional supervision. Therefore, it could be deduced that the extent of prediction between principals' instructional supervision and teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State is very high.

4.2 Test of Hypothesis

Principals' instructional supervision does not significantly predict teachers' job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State

Table 2: Simple Linear Regression Test of extent to which principals’ instructional supervision predicts teachers’ job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom

Variable	Sum of Square	df	Mean square	F-cal.	F- crit	Decision
Regression	47761.388	1	47761.388			
				*sig. 3736.508	3.86	Ho Rejected
Residual	9919.112	776	12.782			

Note: * = Significant at 0.05 alpha level, $df = n-2, 778-2 = 776$

The result of the analysis presented in Table 2 reveals that F- calculated is 3736.508 and F- critical is 3.89 at 0 .05 level of significance. The F- calculated of 3736.508 is greater than the F- critical 3.86. Thus, the null hypothesis that “principals’ instructional supervision does not significantly predict teachers’ job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State.” is rejected. Therefore, principals’ instructional supervision significantly predicts teachers’ job effectiveness in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom South State.

4.3 Finding of the Study

There is a very high extent of prediction between principals’ instructional supervision and teachers’ job effectiveness.

4.4 Discussion of Finding

The result of the Hypothesis shows that the extent to which principals’ instructional supervision predicts teachers’ job effectiveness is significant. This result simply means that when the principal adopts good instructional supervision, it makes teachers more effective on their job. The reason for the outcome of this study may be due to the fact that a principal who sets clear objectives for each day, adapts to change in the work place, plans his time and manages it effectively and considers every aspects of the objectives normally forms a work team in which teachers have the confidence to work in one spirit towards the attainment of the school goals. The finding of this study is in agreement with the research findings of Egbe (2010); Etudor-Eyo Etor, Akuegwu & Etokebe (2021); Sule Arop & Alade (2012); Nzabonimpa (2011), Umaru (2018) and Iroegbu an&d Etudor- Eyo (2016), who found that effective instructional supervision has significant impact on the teachers’ job effectiveness.

5 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Conclusion

The study based on the finding concluded that principals' administrative behaviour in terms of principals' instructional supervision predicts teachers' job effectiveness at a significant extent. It was found out that, it is very necessary for secondary school principals to ensure the utilization of instructional supervision for teachers to improve their capabilities and overall work performance in the school.

5.2 Recommendation

Based on the finding of this study, it was recommended that training principals on the importance of administrative behaviours and most importantly instructional supervision should be government priority. This could be done through staff development programmes. Example: seminars, workshops and conferences.

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